

THE CURRENT STATE OF IMPROVING THE CREATIVE APPROACH IN THE FORMATION OF ECOLOGICAL CONCEPTS IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Аннотация: Ўсиб келаётган ёш авлодда экологик тушунчаларни, яъни атроф-муҳитга масъуллик муносабатини шакллантиришни таъминлайдиган экологик билимлар, қадриятлар, кўникма ва малакалар, қараш ва эътиқодлар, қисқаси, ўқувчиларнинг табиий ва ижтимоий муҳитдаги хилма-хил фаолиятини тартибга солиб турувчи экологик билим, экологик онг ва экологик одоб-ахлоқни таркиб топтириш асосий вазифа қилиб белгиланган. Жумладан, бошланғич синф ўқувчиларида экологияга оид тушунчаларни шакллантиришда креативлик жараёни хулқ-атвор қоидалари, мезонлари миллий ғоянинг ўқувчилар онгида акс этиши, ўқувчилар дунёқарашининг яхлитлиги, объектив оламдаги предмет ва ҳодисаларнинг ўзаро алоқадорлиги бу таълим жараёнида фанлараро алоқадорлик орқали табиат, жамият, техника, инсон ўзаро боғлиқлигини англатади. Дарс жараёнида ўқувчиларнинг олаётган таълим-тарбияси уларнинг шахс сифатидаги инсоний камолотида муҳим ўрин эгаллайди. Ҳаётга бўлган қизиқиш ижобий хислатлар, табиатни муҳофаза қилиш, ҳар бир нарсага муҳим эканлиги назари билан қараш ўқувчиларда экологик тарбиянинг натижаси заминда экологик маданият сифатида намоён бўлиши каби маълумотлар ёритилган.

Калит сўзлар: табиий фанлар, экологик маданият, экологик тарбия, экологик тафаккур, экологик муаммолар, дарс ва дарсдан ташқари машғулотлар, атроф-муҳит, ахборот, самарадорлик, ижтимоий - фойдали меҳнат, кўкаламзорлаштириш.

Abstract: Environmental knowledge, values, skills and competencies, views and beliefs that ensure the formation of ecological concepts, i.e. responsible attitude towards the environment in the growing young generation, in short, ecological knowledge, ecological awareness and the formation of environmental ethics is defined as the main task. In particular, the creative process in the formation of concepts of ecology among elementary school students, the rules of behavior, criteria, the reflection of the national idea in the minds of students, the integrity of the worldview of students, the interrelationship of objects and events in the objective world, in this educational process, the interdependence of nature, society, technology, and man through interdisciplinary communication means. The education and education of students in the course of the lesson occupies an important place in their human maturation as a person. Such information as positive qualities of interest in life, protection of nature, the view that everything is important is reflected in students as a manifestation of environmental culture on the basis of the result of environmental education.

Key words: natural sciences, ecological culture, ecological education, ecological thinking, ecological problems, curricular and extracurricular activities, environment, information, efficiency, social - useful work, greening.

Аннотация: экологические знания, ценности, навыки и умения, взгляды и убеждения, обеспечивающие формирование экологических концепций, то есть ответственного отношения к окружающей среде, у подрастающего поколения синонимы, короче говоря, содержание экологических знаний, экологического сознания и экологической этики, которые регулируют разнообразную деятельность студентов в природной и социальной среде, определяется как основная задача. В частности, творческий процесс в формировании представлений об экологии у младших школьников, правил поведения, критериев, отражение национальной идеи в сознании учащихся, целостность мировоззрения учащихся, взаимосвязь предметов и событий в предметном мире, в этом образовательном процессе взаимообусловленность природы, общества, техники и человека посредством междисциплинарной связи. Образование, которое учащиеся получают на уроке, играет важную роль в их человеческом развитии как личности. Такая информация, как интерес к жизни как к положительным качествам, бережное отношение к природе, взгляд на все как на важное, проявляется как экологическая культура у школьников в результате экологического воспитания.

Ключевые слова: естествознание, экологическая культура, экологическое образование, экологическое мышление, экологические проблемы, учебная и внеучебная деятельность, окружающая среда, информация, эффективность, общественно-полезный труд, экологизация.

In the world, mastering nature from the point of view of ecological logic, that is, understanding, becomes a criterion that determines the content of values. At the same time, the ecological crisis and the historical need to prevent destruction raised these views to the level of theoretical consciousness. Especially with the increase of anthropogenic and man-made impact on nature, the objective need to develop ecological culture has matured. The internal driving mechanism of the development of any historical period depends on the conflicts between nature and society. The tools for solving these conflicts are of urgent importance, in particular, improvement of concepts related to ecology based on a creative approach, development in the conditions of informational education environment.

Today, nature protection has become a common global problem of the world community. In particular, during the past period, along with the reform of all spheres of world society, creation of ecologically stable living conditions for people has become the priority direction of every state policy. In this regard, universal and regional environmental danger, its causes, coordination of relations between man and nature, society and nature, prevention of environmental destruction are among the important problems of today.

In our country, ecology and environmental protection are being developed as a component of the continuous education system. Also, the "Concept of Continuous Environmental Education" has been put into practice, the content of environmental education is being improved, and the material and technical base is being modernized. In the action strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "Prevention of environmental problems that harm the natural environment, population health and gene pool" is defined as an urgent task.¹ Therefore, evaluation of ecology as a multidisciplinary field, ethical nature and modern content of ecology, innovative thinking and application of new approaches to the educational process serve to ensure the effectiveness of environmental education.

In order to ensure the implementation of the Decree No. PF-5024 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 21, 2017 "On improving the state management system in

the field of ecology and environmental protection", the implementation of mechanisms representing environmental safety and stability determines the priority tasks of the sustainable development of ecological and ethical relations.

Therefore, theoretical ecological knowledge (ecological thinking) and the unity of activities carried out in the way of environment and nature protection serve to form ecological culture. Ecological thinking is the mental expression of concepts regarding the current state of nature and the environment, their protection, and it is manifested as a complex socio-psychological phenomenon. Ecological activity means a set of actions carried out to ensure the protection of nature and the environment based on ecological knowledge.

The following tasks should be solved in order to improve elementary school students' understanding of ecology based on a creative approach:

- to further increase the environmental knowledge acquired by students in the educational process.
- to enrich their perception of nature and environmental ecology.
- formation of students' belief that protection of nature and environment is a social necessity.
- to educate students in environmental activity skills and abilities and to achieve their active participation in the process of ensuring nature and environment protection.

Improvement of the concepts of ecology in elementary school students based on a creative approach in the form of class and extracurricular activities, i.e. roundtables, excursions, debates, creative contests, meetings, social and useful work (greening) and organizing and encouraging conversations, observations, practical activities organization using such methods ensures creativity in students.

Also, the use of ethical conversation, discussion, conference, seminar and debate in the process of organizing creativity in the formation of concepts related to ecology among elementary school students gives its positive results.

Establishing the correct attitude towards nature in students, instilling love, achieving environmental cleanliness is an important step in the way of solving environmental problems. Ecological education is an educational process aimed at providing students with theoretical ecological knowledge in a consistent, systematic and continuous manner.

The process of creativity in the formation of concepts of ecology in elementary school students is the reflection of behavioral rules, criteria, as well as the national idea in the minds of students. Creativity, moral activity skills and moral culture are established in the process of education and training on moral, socio-ideological, economic, legal, aesthetic and environmental topics, discussions, debates, selflessly working in various fields of the national economy, science, culture, development It is formed through the effective use of information about the life and activities of individuals who make the name of the Republic of Uzbekistan famous in the world by achieving high levels of success in the fields of publishing and sports, and who make their due contribution to the increase of its prestige.

Creativity is also important in the formation of students' worldview, and it is desirable to achieve the unity of mind, emotions and behavior in its effective organization. After all, the occurrence of certain shortcomings in their unity has a negative effect on the development of students as perfect individuals. A worldview is a system of dialectical views and beliefs that determine the development of the content of nature, society, human thinking and personal activity.

It is definitely necessary to take into account the emotional environment when improving the creative approach to the formation of ecological concepts in elementary school students. Through his interests, the student tries to acquire knowledge about the surrounding natural environment and its riches, secrets of nature, flora and fauna.

The natural and social environment surrounding a person has a great influence on personality formation. The importance of the natural environment is the leader in the formation of concepts of environmental education among primary school students. Cognition begins with the perception of the environment and is summarized in thinking. Only when the teacher pays attention to the study of the laws of nature, taking into account the cognitive processes of the students, he can give effective results in the formation of concepts related to environmental education in the personality of the child.

Understanding, knowing, and feeling the connection between natural phenomena is an important principle in the formation of concepts related to ecological education. As a result of the student's knowledge of the interaction and influence between natural phenomena, it will be possible to form concepts related to environmental education and to awaken the feeling of conscious attitude to nature.

Today, it is the demand of the time for students of primary school age to become ecologically literate. Because environmental problems in the world can be prevented through environmental literacy. There are a number of issues that can be influenced based on a creative approach to ecological concepts, the main of which can be considered as the following (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Scheme of the component of the problem of exposure to ecological concepts based on a creative approach

Today, in the state education standard, curriculum and science programs, knowledge, skills, qualifications and competences in environmental content are not comprehensively enriched is to develop specific mechanisms for the formation of environmental culture in students.

In fact, the goal of teaching natural sciences to elementary school students based on a creative approach is the formation of concepts related to environmental education in the process of teaching is a complex and multifaceted process, which can be solved by abandoning consumerist attitudes towards nature, inculcating responsibility for the natural and artificially created environment in the growing young generation. will be done.

Formation of concepts related to ecological education in the course of classes for elementary school students is dialectical knowledge that interprets the harmony of nature and society (man) as a natural-historical, progressive, social problem. Man not only moves various types of plants and animals, plants and factories to other places, but also fundamentally changes the climate and ecology of the place where he lives. But at the current stage of society's development, environmental problems are interpreted as an actual social problem that does not depend on the system.

Improving the creative approach to the formation of ecological concepts in elementary school students is carried out on the example of natural sciences. Therefore, in the process of teaching natural sciences in elementary grades, improving the concepts of ecology based on a creative approach, educating students to be responsible for the environment, to establish universal and moral-ecological values, ethics, caution, thrift, cleanliness, health, environmental protection It is important to rely on the thoughts of the educational content. For example, whoever plants a sapling, or sows a crop, and people, birds, and animals benefit from their harvest, this is also a charity for that person, Abdullah Muhammad ibn Ismail al-Bukhari writes. This tool emphasizes that the students help to care for every plant planted in the school without breaking it.

The methodological basis for improving the creative approach to the formation of ecological concepts in primary grades covers the following content:

- the essence of the student's personality is manifested in the set of interactions between nature, society and technology;
- the student's attitude to nature depends on relying on the universal value of morals - al-Bukhari and al-Tirmidhi hadiths;
- forming a responsible attitude towards nature and the environment is an important goal of primary education, which shows that the student's personality has matured in all aspects;
- responsible attitude to nature is formed on the basis of harmonious development of its various: social, economic, spiritual, educational, ideological, political, legal aspects.

Periods of formation of concepts related to environmental education in elementary school students, indicators of their mastery levels, and the ability to be curious are mainly explained as follows:

1st period. The emergence of an ecological vision, its perception, and the need for it;

2nd period. Creating the necessary pedagogical environment for the realization of the idea of ecological education;

3rd period. Connecting solutions to issues that need to be resolved;

4th period. Using the proposed methodology, improvement of concepts related to ecological education based on a creative approach.

The effect of the curiosity characteristic of students on the effectiveness of the lesson varies in rural, district and urban areas. For example, the work of people in the village is different from that in the city, or the nature of the village may be different from the nature of the city. Living things live under the influence of various phenomena of the external environment. In particular, environmental factors also have an impact on living beings. We all know abiotic, biotic and anthropogenic factors of ecological factors. Among the environmental factors, the anthropogenic factor forms environmental problems through its influence on nature and its components.

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